

Pasteurella Multocida Infection in Emu (*Dromaius Novaehollandiae*)

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Abstract

Fowl cholera is one of the earliest reported septicaemic bacterial diseases of poultry caused by Gram negative *Pasteurella multocida*, which is characterized by high mortality. A dead Emu from an organized farm, Puducherry was brought to the Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Veterinary Education and Research, Puducherry for diagnosis. Heart blood smear and the impression smears prepared from liver and lung indicated the presence of bipolar organisms. Heart blood cultured on blood agar at 37°C for 48 hours revealed colonies of *Pasteurella* species. The isolate was identified as *Pasteurella multocida* by detailed biochemical and pathogenicity studies. Antimicrobial sensitivity studies indicated that the organism was sensitive to Enrofloxacin, Kanamycin and Ampicillin. The isolate was subjected to PCR assay with species specific primers for *Pasteurella multocida* for confirmation. The PCR assay yielded a product of 460bp specific to *Pasteurella multocida*.

Key words: Emu, Pasteurellosis, Isolation, Characterization, Antimicrobial.

Avian pasteurellosis (Fowl cholera) is a septicaemic disease of domestic and wild birds and is distributed world-wide. The disease is characterized by high mortality associated with significant losses to poultry industry (Hansen and Hirsh, 1989). The disease caused by *Pasteurella multocida* serovar A, is a small, Gram negative cocco-bacillary, non-motile, non-spore forming, facultative anaerobe belongs to the family Pasteurellaceae (Quinn *et al.*, 1994). Avian strain of *Pasteurella* infection is largely restricted to chickens, turkeys, geese, ducks and

wild fowls. The diseases in pigeons seem to be rare (Bhat *et al.*, 2002). This paper is to document the first reported occurrence of avian cholera in emu from an organized farm, Puducherry.

Materials and Methods

A dead Emu from an organized Emu farm at Villianur, Puducherry was brought to the Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Veterinary Education and Research, Puducherry for diagnosis. General condition of the carcass is fair, blood oozing was noticed from natural orifices, partial rigor mortis was observed on post mortem findings, lungs were severely congested and consolidation were noted, pinpoint haemorrhages are evident in the proventriculus, liver showed necrotic foci. Impression smears from heart blood, liver and organs like lung, proventriculus, spleen and brain were also collected for further studies. Impression smears from liver, lung and heart blood stained using Leishman's stain are screened for bacterial and parasitic organisms. Sheep blood and MacConkey agars were used as primary culture media for isolation of organisms from the samples according to methods described by Quinn *et al.* (loc. cit). Triturated tissues were inoculated on Sheep blood agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Next day non-haemolytic single colony from Sheep blood agar was transferred to MacConkey agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The isolates which failed to grow on MacConkey agar were preliminary presumed to be *P. multocida*. Single non-haemolytic colony of these isolates was picked up from primary culture and streaked on fresh Sheep blood agar plate and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to obtain single colony of pure culture of the isolates. The smear from culture was stained with Gram staining for the purity

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and morphology of the organisms. Then the cultures were subjected for biochemical tests, *Pasteurella multocida* -PCR based detection and in vitro antibiotic sensitivity. *P. multocida* isolates were identified by biochemical tests viz., Catalase, Oxidase, Indole, Methyl red, Voges proskauer, Nitrate reduction, Urease test, H₂S in TSI, Beta -Galactosidase activity and Ornithine and fermentation of sugars viz., glucose, maltose, sucrose, mannose, lactose and inositol as per methods described by Barrow and Felthem (1993). The isolates were subjected to in vitro antibiotic sensitivity as per method described by Bauer *et al.* (1966). The antibiotic discs were obtained from HiMedia Laboratories Pvt.Ltd., Mumbai. The results were interpreted as per chart furnished by the manufacturer. To study In vivo pathogenicity of *Pasteurella multocida* strains isolated from emu, 0.2 ml of 18 hours culture was inoculated intra-peritoneally into the SPF-white mice and observed for 72 hours. If the mice died, the inoculated strains were re-isolated from their organs, such as livers and spleens (Koch, 1893; Wilson *et al.*, 1993).

PCR was carried out using *P. multocida* specific primer pairs Forward primer KMT1SP6 5'-GCT GTA AAC GAA CTC GCC AC - 3', Reverse primer KM T1T7 5' - ATC CGC TAT TTA CCC AGT GG - 3' which will specifically amplify KMT1 gene of avian *P. multocida* serovar A with the product size of 460bp (Townsend *et al.* 1998). Colony PCR (*Pasteurella multocida* -PCR) was performed using PCR protocol described by Dutta *et al.* (2001). The total volume of reaction mixture is 25 µl consisting of PCR buffer (10X) 2.5 µl, MgCl₂ (25mM) 1.5 µl, DNTPs (10 mM) 0.5 µl Forward primer KMT1SP6 (10 pmol/ml), 0.5 µl, reverse primer KMT1T7 (10 pmol/ml), 0.5 µl, Taq DNA polymerase (3U/ ml) 0.3 µl, Template DNA is single colony and distilled water 19.2 µl. The conditions for the PCR assay were initial denaturation at 94°C for 5 minutes, followed by thirty cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 1min, annealing at 58°C for 1 minutes and extension at 72°C for 1 minutes, with the final extension at 72°C for 5 minutes. The PCR amplification was carried out in an automated thermal cycler (Eppendorf Master Cycler, Germany). PCR products along with 50 bp DNA ladder electrophoresed in 1.5% agarose gel containing

ethidium bromide (5 µl /100 ml). PCR products were visualized as a single fluorescent band of 460bp under UV light.

Results and Discussion

Impression smears from liver, lung and heart blood stained using Leishman's stain revealed the presence of bipolar organisms. On isolation non haemolytic colonies on sheep blood agar with sweetish odour and no Growth on Mac conkey's agar were suggestive for *P. multocida*, the isolates were found to be Gram negative coccobacillary rods. On the bases of cultural, morphological and biochemical characters (Table I and II) the isolate is confirmed as *P. multocida*. These results are in agreement with Barrow and Felthem (*loc. cit.*).

Fig 1. Confirmation by *Pasteurella multocida* PCR using KMT1SP6 and KMT1T7 primer pair Lane 1- Negative control, Lane 2-Emu isolate, Lane 3- positive control, Lane 4-100 base pair ladder.

Table I. Morphological and biochemical characters *Pasteurella multocida* isolated from **Emu**.

Cowan and Steel's manual for identification of medical bacteria 1 st stage table biochemical test	Results
Grams reaction	Gram negative coccobacilli
Capsule	+
Motility	-
Growth in air	+
Growth anaerobically	+
Growth on Mac conkey's agar	no growth
Hemolysis on blood agar	no haemolysis
Catalase	+
Oxidase	+
O/F	Fermentative

Kumar *et al.* (1996) recovered 43 isolates of *P. multocida* from different animals and birds. Biochemical and sugar fermentation tests revealed all the 43 isolates were negative for inulin, lactose, salicin, maltose, rhamnose, inositol and dextrin while the same were positive for dextrose, mannose and fructose. They also reported variation in sugar fermentation reactions within the same serotype however oxidase, gelatin, indole, urease, nitrate and growth on MCA were similar for all the isolates.

In the antibiotic sensitivity test the emu *P. multocida* isolate is sensitive to Enrofloxacin, Kanamycin, Ampicillin, Tetracycline and resistant to Amikacin and Gentamicin. The bacterial organisms over a period of time change their antibiogram patterns and develop resistance against commonly used chemotherapeutic agents. Aye *et al.* (2001) carried out antibiotic sensitivity of *P. multocida* of turkey origin. They found that the majority of the isolates were susceptible to amikacin, ampicillin, ceftiofur, cephalothin, enrofloxacin, florfenicol, gentamicin, neomycin, novobiocin, oxacillin with 2 % Sodium chloride, sarafloxacin, tilmicosin and trimethoprim with sulphadiazine and resistant to clindamicin, penicillin-G, tiamutin and tylosin. Balakrishnan and Mini (2001) isolated and studied four strains of *P. multocida* of avian origin for drug resistance pattern. The isolates were found susceptible to oxytetracycline,

Table II. Biochemical characters *Pasteurella multocida* isolated from **Emu**

Cowan and Steel's manual for identification of medical bacteria 2 nd stage table biochemical test	Results
Indole test	+
Methy Red	-
Voges proskauer	-
Nitrate reduction	+
Urease test	-
H ₂ S in TSI	-
Beta -Galactosidase activity	-
Sugar fermentation test	
Glucose	+
Sucrose	+
Maltose	-
Mannose	+
Inositol	-
Lactose	-

pefloxacin, tetracycline, and streptomycin and resistant to furazolidone, metronidazole and nalidixic acid. Moderate sensitivity was observed to chloramphenicol, gentamicin, kanamycin and penicillin-G.

In the pathogenicity study 0.2 ml of 18 hours culture was inoculated intra-peritoneally into the SPF-white mice and observed for 72 hours. The mice died within 24h post inoculation. Bipolar shaped organisms could be demonstrated in the heart blood smears by Leishman's staining. The same inoculated *Pasteurella multocida* Strain was isolated from the dead mice (Koch. *loc.cit*). Tirumurugaan *et al.* (2004) performed pathogenicity test of five isolates of *P. multocida* in mice which were obtained from field cases from different farms in Namakkal. Five mice each were inoculated intraperitoneally with 1000 CFU in 0.1 ml of Trypticase broth. They found that deaths occurring over the next 24 hrs and similar results were also observed by Wilson, *et al.*, (*loc. cit*).

The *Pasteurella multocida* PCR produced an amplified product of 460 bp size by using the primer pair KMT1SP6 and KMT1T7 by amplifying KMT1 gene fragment from avian *P. multocida* strain (Fig 1). Townsend *et al.* (*loc.*

cit) reported that *P. multocida* specific PCR will provide a rapid, sensitive method for detection of clinically infected birds with *P. multocida* showed that PCR amplification preferred directly on bacterial colonies or cultures represents and extremely rapid, sensitive method of *P. multocida* identification. Dutta *et al.* (*loc. cit*) also carried out *Pasteurella multocida* PCR using various serotypes of *P. multocida*. They also used mixed bacterial culture lysate containing *P. multocida* and got similar results as obtained in pure culture. So it is evident from their study that the other bacterial contamination does not affect specificity of PCR based identification of *P. multocida* isolates. Similar results were also reported by Javia (2004)

Summary

Fowl cholera is a septicaemic bacterial disease of poultry. It is one of the earliest reported diseases of chicken caused by Gram negative *Pasteurella multocida* and is characterized by high mortality. A dead Emu from an organized farm, Puducherry was brought to the Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Veterinary Education and Research, Puducherry for diagnosis. Heart blood smear and the impression smears prepared from liver and lung indicated the presence of bipolar organisms. Heart blood cultured on blood agar when incubated at 37°C for 48 hours revealed colonies of *Pasteurella species*. The isolate was identified as *Pasteurella multocida* by detailed biochemical, pathogenicity and molecular studies. Antimicrobial sensitivity studies indicated that the organism was sensitive to Enrofloxacin, Kanamycin and Ampicillin. The isolate were subjected to PCR assay with species specific

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